

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 680395.

Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

H2020-SPIRE-2015 - RIA n° 680395

Start Date: 14th **September 2015**

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Deliverable Report

D8.4.4_WP8_EMH 4th Semi-annual newsletter

Public

Author(s): Mathilde BOUCHER (EMH)

Task No. : 8.4

Deliverable No. : 8.4.4

Issue Date: 15.09.2017

Number of pages: 17

Identifier: D8.4.4_WP8_EMH

Summary:

This is the fourth of ROMEO's e-newsletters. The e-newsletters are released twice a year. This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created, sent and what makes up the mailing list.

The newsletter is then displayed to 94 subscribers.

The appendices display the full versions of the editorial, news and interviews introduced in the newsletter.

Document history and validation

When	Who	Type	Comments
13.09.17	Mathilde BOUCHER	Preparation version 1 (V1)	

Author(s):	Mathilde BOUCHER (EMH)	Approved by the Coordinator : M. O. Kristen Date: 19.09.2017
Reviewer(s):	Marc Kristen	

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1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to the WordPress and MailPoet Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically as emails. The software splits the mailing list and doesn't send the e-newsletter to more than 30 persons at a time so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Subscribers

We have created 3 mailing lists for the different communication purposes that we may have.

- List 1: all the persons working for ROMEO within ROMEO's partners;
- List 2: other people within ROMEO's partners, not working directly on the project but who might be interested in the project
- List 3: other people not part of ROMEO that partners want to inform about the project.

All 9 partners had the opportunity to send names for these three categories and we collected a total of 94 people.

ROMEO's 4th e-newsletter was sent to all 3 mailing lists on **Monday 4 September 2017**.

3. Newsletter 4

Please click [here](#) to read ROMEO's 4th newsletter online (or use the following link: http://www.romeo-h2020.eu/?wysija-page=1&controller=email&action=view&email_id=11&wysijap=subscriptions)

Screenprints of the newsletter are displayed on the next pages.

See appendices for all the links to pdf documents that can be opened when browsing the newsletter online.

Newsletter

CATALYTIC REACTOR METHODOLOGIES
FOR PROCESS INTENSIFICATION

Follow the official Twitter account for the ROMEIO project
[@romeo123EU](https://twitter.com/romeo123EU) and use #ROMEIOH2020 when you tweet a message
related to the project !

Editorial

Welcome to the fourth newsletter of ROMEIO.

After a beginning of 2017, which had been rich of meetings for the ROMEIO's team, it was time to take stock of what has been accomplished since September 2015 and what still needs to be done.

ROMEIO's partners, who are developing a new reactor (two-in-one) concept using homogeneous catalysis and membrane technology to carry out chemical synthesis and downstream processing in a single step, have submitted the Project Periodic Report in May 2017. [...] Although we all know that there is still a lot of work to build ROMEIO's two demo plants, the report clearly shows that we have already made a huge step forward to achieve our goals. I would like to thank again all of the ROMEIO's workers for their great work!

Read the full editorial [here](#).

ROMEIO relies on the bests !

The Université de Caen Normandie (France) is giving Prof. Dr. Miguel A. Bañares, full Research Professor at CSIC in Madrid, the Doctor Honoris Causa degree in recognition to his seminal contribution in the implementation of the advanced "Operando" methodology that characterizes catalytic materials while they are

working.

All the members of the ROMEIO's consortium are joining to congratulate their colleague. We are really proud to rely on the bests!

Read more about his award [here](#) and find Miguel's interview below.

ROMEIO highlighted in the CBI Symposium

Alexander Weiss has presented on Wednesday the 10th of May a poster referring to ROMEIO in the frame of a symposium of his Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering (CBI) at the FAU in Erlangen.

Read more and download the entire poster [here](#).

Focus on Miguel A. Bañares

Miguel is Full Research Professor at CSIC in Madrid, recently awarded doctor honoris causa of University of Caen Normandy (UNICAEN)

"I have always been very fond of science. Exploring is something I like. [...]"

ROMEIO's idea to immobilize ionic liquid in a porous frame, to control the distribution of this ionic liquid into it and to be able to get control on selectivity is amazing!"

Read the full interview [here](#).

Focus on Alexander Limper

Alex is a PhD candidate at the RWTH Aachen University in Germany. He is working since last November on modelling mass and heat transfer in membrane reactors.

"The most part of my job consist in dealing with challenges that come up on the way and that you

didn't see coming. [...] I like when it is demanding. By that way you can push yourself to achieve something you wouldn't have thought you could!"

Read the full interview [here](#).

Focus on Jennifer Haßelberg

Jennifer is a process engineer at Evonik in Germany working on process intensification by membrane reactors.

"I really like to work with the operators and production engineers in our plants. Those are the guys with the most interesting stories and experiences. [...] If ROMEIO is economically efficient at the end, we would be happy to inaugurate the first industrial application for a membrane reactor."

Read the full interview [here](#).

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4. Appendices

4.1 Editorial by Prof. Robert Franke, ROMEIO's coordinator;

Editorial
Fourth Newsletter, **September 2017**

Welcome to the fourth newsletter of ROMEIO.

After a beginning of 2017, which had been rich of meetings for the ROMEIO's team, it was time to take stock of what has been accomplished since September 2015 and what still needs to be done.

ROMEIO's partners, who are **developing a new reactor (two-in-one) concept using homogeneous catalysis and membrane technology to carry out chemical synthesis and downstream processing in a single step**, have submitted the Project Periodic Report in May 2017.

Reaction conditions for the membrane and purity requirements of the product have been determined, as well as the support structure for membrane modules. The first separation concept (separation of Hydrogen) has been extended and a new one has been set up to produce two valuable products: CO₂ (in the first step) and Hydrogen (in a second step). First results from catalyst tests on support structure are evaluated.

In order to develop a rigorous model for the membrane reactor module and the chemical processes in which the modules are applied, boundary conditions are now determined. With the objective to shift the developed process concept from feasibility towards a running process under near industrial conditions, basic principles and information for a life time cycle assessment for the module have been collected and a first assessment structure has been set up. Requirements on reactor module and feed conditions have been specified.

Although we all know that there is still a lot of work to build ROMEIO's two demo plants, the report clearly shows that we have already made a huge step forward to achieve our goals. **I would like to thank again all of the ROMEIO's workers for their great work!**

Due to a special occasion, we had to reschedule the **next Project Meeting in Madrid**, which was originally planned in October. According to partners' availabilities, ROMEIO's next Progress Meeting will be held on the 15th and 16th of November 2017, in Madrid.

The reason for the rescheduling was a very special one: our colleague Miguel Bañares from CSIC is awarded doctor honoris causa of University of Caen Normandy (UNICAEN)! You can read more about it in this newsletter.

As usual, you can also find out more about people behind the ROMEIO project. In this issue, you'll get a glimpse into the daily working life of Miguel, full Researcher Professor at CSIC in Madrid, Alexander, PhD candidate at the RWTH Aachen University in Germany and Jennifer Haßelberg, process engineer at Evonik (Germany).

Please feel free to contact us via our website (www.romeio-h2020.eu) should you have any question or comment. Enjoy your reading, and don't forget to follow us on twitter! [@romeo123EU](https://twitter.com/romeo123EU)

Prof. Robert Franke - Project Coordinator- Evonik

4.2 News about Miguel's award

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Miguel Bañares (CSIC) awarded doctor honoris causa

Jun 2017

0 Comment

All the members of the ROMEO's consortium are joining to congratulate their colleague Miguel A. Bañares, full Research Professor at CSIC in Madrid. We are really proud to rely on the bests!

The Université de Caen Normandie (France) is giving Prof. Dr. Miguel A. Bañares the Doctor Honoris Causa degree in recognition to his seminal contribution in the implementation of an advanced methodology that characterizes catalytic materials while they are working, digressing from the traditional approach of catalytic studies that combined the characterization of the fresh and used catalyst, missing the actual state of the catalyst at work.

This innovative path, which is now highly praised, is called "operando" methodology, term that Bañares coined. "Operando" is the present continuous tense in Latin of operare, i.e., "working". It also acknowledges Bañares' collaborative work with Prof. Dr. Marco Daturi's group at Université de Caen to expand this methodology to real working shaped catalysts and the combination of two molecular spectroscopies: Raman and infrared.

CSIC, as leader of the porous ceramic monoliths fabrication in the frame of ROMEO (task 3 of the WP2, Membrane development) already shows us new insights and research prospects to go further!

4.3 ROMEIO's poster presented in the CBI Symposium

Reactor Optimization by Membrane Enhanced Operation: Process intensification with membrane reactors (ROMEIO)

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What is ROMEIO?

- Research and Innovation project within the **European Union's Horizon 2020** research and innovation program
- Focus on new reactor concept:
 - Reduction of **energy consumption by 80%** and **emissions by up to 90%** in industrial catalytic gas-phase reactions
- 9 partners** team up for **4 years** to demonstrate the technical feasibility of this reactor concept
- Started in **September 2015** with an EU budget of **6 million euros**

- Combination of **different building blocks** (membrane, support, catalyst) into **single reactor module**

- Gas phase **hydroformylation** reaction as case study
 - Side product difficulty

Using the SILP Concept for ROMEIO

Supported Ionic Liquid Phase (SILP) Catalysts:

- Innovative immobilization concept for gas phase applications
- Heterogenization of homogeneous catalysts
 - Free flowing powder
 - Homogeneous catalyst phase (Ionic liquid + precursor + ligand) impregnated into pores of support material

- Homogeneous Catalysis:
 - Selectivity
 - Reaction rate
 - Catalyst recovery

- Heterogeneous Catalysis:
 - Catalyst recovery
 - Simple systems
 - Selectivity

First Catalytic Results

Reactor set-up & preparation procedure:

Support screening:

- Promising results for ceramic and CNT's as novel SILP supports

Impregnated monolith:

Impregnated & membrane coated monolith:

- First successful application** of Supported Ionic Liquid Membrane (SILM) module

Summary

- Investigation of novel membrane reactor concept
- Combination of already studied building blocks into a single membrane reactor module
 - Novel support materials
 - Membrane functionality
 - SILP catalyst
- Teamwork of different partners on support fabrication, membrane coating & SILP impregnation
- Successful screening of suitable support materials
- Establishment of membrane reactor set-up
- Successful application of monolith supported SILP catalysts
- First investigation of SILM module:
 - Successful preparation process at different partner sites
 - First catalytic active membrane module

4.4 Full interview of Miguel Bañares (CSIC)

European Research & Innovation Project
Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

Interview with Miguel A. Bañares
Full Research Professor at CSIC in Madrid

“ ROMEIO’s idea to immobilize ionic liquid in a porous frame, to control the distribution of this ionic liquid into it and to be able to get control on selectivity is amazing! ”

Hi, Miguel ! Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself ?

I have always been very fond of science. Exploring is something I like. I got my degree in chemistry and then started my research career in the field of heterogeneous catalysis.

I guess I was lucky because during my PhD I had the opportunity to start using in situ Raman spectroscopy during a stay at Lehigh University. That was very informative because I got a lot of insight into what makes a catalyst active and I realized that I liked characterization, but also that getting close to the reactivity was important.

Then I went for a PostDoc in Indiana at Notre Dame University, where we were playing with infrared spectroscopy. We were looking at the structural changes of many catalysts, observing at the same time how the systems were becoming increasingly active.

When I went back to Madrid, in 1995, I got my position of scientist at the Institute for Catalysis of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). In 2000 I promoted to senior scientist, and in 2008 to research professor.

What is your favorite work subject ?

All my activities have always been about making emphasis on characterizing catalysts, catalytic systems and even catalytic reactions, mainly with Raman spectroscopy and a lot of cooperation! My research activities have typically been focusing on understanding the relationship between their structure and their performance. The problem is that you have to do characterization during the chemical act.

That is what I called the “Operando” methodology, because separately they don’t really connect. Actually, it is quite a simple idea, but few people had been doing it.

Date of interview : May 2017
Publication : August 2017

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We have started to investigate using the operando methodology in 2000 with few other groups in Europe.

The idea is not only treating samples in different environments but also looking at the structure of the real working material, measuring its activity simultaneously. That's what makes the difference, trying to get into the real things. I have always been moving in that direction.

“ That’s what makes the difference, trying to get into the real things. ”

What does your daily job look like?

Paperwork, travelling, paperwork, travelling and... paperwork. More seriously, daily experimental operando work is distracting and very demanding because making real time characterization means that you must have spectrometers, online activity measurements and catalytic reactors working correctly, and simultaneously. Hopefully, if you like it you don't complain!

I enjoy managing people working on these experimentations and also doing a lot of collaborative work. The operando methodology is becoming popular and often nice and challenging collaborations arise. For example, right now, we have 4 visitors in our relatively small group who come from Hong-Kong, Italy, Brazil and Argentina to do operando Raman studies. It is very exciting because each group poses a different scientific and/or technical challenge. We are dealing with really diverse kinds of reactions, so, I learn a lot!

“ I enjoy managing people working on operando experimentations and also doing a lot of collaborative work. ”

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We heard that you have been awarded doctor honoris causa of University of Caen Normandy (UNICAEN). Congratulations! Can you please tell us a little bit more about it? How do you feel regarding this award?

I see it as a way of recognizing my contribution to the implementation of the operando methodology, and subsequently the importance of the methodology itself.

I know they are giving this recognition only every ten years, so I am overwhelmed. Although I'm not the only one, we are 6 awardees from 6 different fields of knowledge; it makes me feel a high responsibility! There has been a really tough selection so I feel really obliged. I really have to keep up my work to be at the level this distinction implies.

“ Now we have managed to obtain pretty straight tubes of the composition and shape desired, which was quite a challenge! ”

What excites you in ROME?

The frame of ROME is challenging, with the objective of optimizing the reactions performance applying constraints to the transport of some components. The idea to immobilize ionic liquid in a porous frame, to control the distribution of this ionic liquid into it and to be able to get control on selectivity is amazing!

Our contribution in CSIC is basically about making the membranes structure.

It could be interesting in the future to say ok, now that we have the system working and we can compare several systems, we can get real time profiles to know what is happening with the membranes and with the molecules absorbed by the membranes. But before running, you have to walk. We are now making a system that will work. It would be really interesting to tackle this in the future, but it is not in the program of ROME.

Date of interview : May 2017
Publication : August 2017

What are, according to you, the major challenges to be overcome in ROMEIO?

Our group should be able to get a good control on the actual shape and mechanical resistance of the membrane. Now we have managed to obtain pretty straight tubes of the composition and shape desired, which was quite a challenge! We are able to engineer them accurately. To my opinion, the great challenge that we have is to get the opportunity to control the acidity and the porosity of this material.

Thanks for your time Miguel, and all the best for your projects!

“ It could be interesting in the future to say ok, now that we have the system working and we can compare several systems, we can get real time profiles to know what is happening with the membranes and with the molecules absorbed by the membranes. But before running, you have to walk. ”

The Institute of Catalysis and Petrochemistry is a research center belonging to the Spanish Council for Scientific Research (CSIC), an agency under the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO), and is framed within the Area of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, one of eight scientific-technical areas in which the CSIC divides its research activities.

www.icp.csic.es/

Date of interview : May 2017
Publication : August 2017

ROMEIO in brief

Funded by European Commission
(Horizon 2020)

Start date:
14 September 2015

End date:
13 September 2019

Budget:
6 Million €

Contacts:
Evonik - DE
Project Coordinator - Prof. Robert Franke
Scientific Coordinator - Dr. Frank Stenger
Project Manager - Dr. Marc Oliver Kristen

H2020-EU.2.1.5
Project Reference: 680395

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4.5 Full interview of Alexander Limper (RWTH Aachen University)

European Research & Innovation Project
Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

Interview with Alexander Limper
PhD candidate at the RWTH Aachen University, Germany

“ I wish we will be able to evaluate the feasibility of a membrane reactor for any gas phase reaction and propose a handy tool to help with the design of such a reactor. ”

Hi, Alex ! Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself ?

I graduated in mechanical engineering at RWTH Aachen University in September 2016 with a specialization in chemical engineering and computational fluid dynamics. Having investigated fluid flow and mass transfer in hollow fiber membrane modules, ROMEIO appeared to be a rather fitting project. Beside fluid flow, the model has to further account for reaction and possibly heat transfer.

I enjoy the work environment at AVT, with many research assistants working on countless projects with great motivation. AVT, Aachener VerfahrensTechnik, means Aachen Chemical Engineering and combines 7 chairs of RWTH working on different topics. I am working with chemical process engineering, which focuses on the development and application of membrane technology.

The PhD I am undertaking within the ROMEIO project since last November is more specifically about modelling mass and heat transfer in membrane reactors.

What does your daily job look like, as a research assistant?

It is hard to define one standard day because the most part of it consists in dealing with challenges that come up on the way and that you didn't see coming.

For instance, the implementation of the energy balance in the model looks easy on paper with the basic conservation equations. But if you implement it in the model, you might face problems with convergence and you will have to go on a hunt for the reason which might just be a certain value approaching zero or a mis-

Date of interview : June 2017
Publication : August 2017

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take in your code. It can be exciting and it can be frustrating as well. But if you come up with a solution at the end it is very stimulating.

So my job is more a day by day job, working with students, who help me with the model and also Morten Logemann with the membrane coating.

How do you collaborate with Morten, who is working at the RWTH Aachen University on the membrane development?

Morten and I are not working in the same WP of ROMEIO but in Aachen we have a really close collaboration, working in the same office. I think it is very important to keep a global vision of the project activities.

“ I enjoy the work environment at AVT, with many research assistants working on countless projects with great motivation. ”

For example, about the water gas shift reaction, we had to adapt our approach because we saw that we will not be able to produce a membrane selective enough for a hydrogen separation. Now we have adapted the water gas shift reaction, so we will try to find a CO₂ selective membrane. It will be important for the modelling as well, not only for the membrane coating or process development. So, it is important that we, in RWTH, are cooperating together but also with the other partners of the project.

What excites you in ROMEIO?

The project is a very interdisciplinary project. We have to coordinate a lot with other partners. The aim is to design not only a functional membrane reactor for several selected

large-scale industrial applications, but also a methodology to evaluate feasibility of this technology for any other given reaction/separation problem is very ambitious.

“ The most part of my job consist in dealing with challenges that come up on the way and that you didn't see coming. ”

Developing a model is quite demanding because we are aiming for a very general model to be applied to a lot of possible reactions. So it's not just another application.

I like that it is demanding. By that way you can push yourself to achieve something you wouldn't have thought you could! It may prove to be a hard task to fulfill until the very end, but I am sure that with this ambition, we will also have achieved quite more than we expected in the beginning.

What is your objective is the frame of the project? Could you give us a concrete example of a benefit that could be obtained thanks to ROMEIO?

Within the methodology development, we aim to develop a model that shall be a helpful tool for a broad range of applications.

“ It is important that we, in RWTH, are cooperating together but also with the other partners of the project. ”

Date of interview : June 2017
Publication : August 2017

I wish we will be able to evaluate the feasibility of a membrane reactor for any gas phase reaction and propose a handy tool to help with the design of such a reactor.

I know that you are attending ROMEO's progress meeting in Madrid next November. What are your expectations?

We already have regular telephone conferences, which are nice to get everybody heard. But with everybody on the phone it is sometimes hard if you have questions for someone in particular.

I hope this meeting will give chances to coordinate stuff like that, as already done during the previous projects meetings. We will also have a lot more time to discuss and get to know each

“ I like when it is demanding. By that way you can push yourself to achieve something you wouldn't have thought you could! ”

RWTH Aachen University (Chair of Chemical Engineering - AVT.CVT), has extensive experience in the development of membrane integrated processes.

RWTH is responsible for the development of the architecture of the membrane reactor in the ROMEO project and will also model the membrane reactor.

<http://www.avt.rwth-aachen.de/>

Date of interview : June 2017
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H2020-EU.2.1.5
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4.6 Full interview of Jennifer Haßelberg (Evonik)

European Research & Innovation Project
Reactor Optimisation by Membrane Enhanced Operation

Interview with Jennifer Haßelberg
Process Engineer at EVONIK,
Technology & Infrastructure GmbH, Germany

“ I really like to work with the operators and production engineers in our plants. Those are the guys with the most interesting stories and experiences.”

Hi, Jennifer ! Can you please tell us a little bit about yourself ?

In school I always loved science and art, but becoming a professional artist has never been an option because that should remain my private hobby.

So there was math and chemistry and that perfectly fitted to become a chemical engineer. I still love the mindset that we do our work for a specific reason and goal – to make things easier, cheaper, sustainable... Also technology is developing so fast that there is always more and more to learn.

What is your favorite work subject ?

Process intensification by Membrane reactors, of course! In addition I really like to work with the operators and production engineers in our plants. Those are the guys with the most interesting stories and experiences.

What does your daily job look like?

I do meet a lot of different people and that is what makes it super interesting.

We have many of telcos with project partners around the world and video conferences with colleagues from Evonik which tell about their projects and innovative ideas. We solve problems together so everybody can profit from another's experience.

What excites you in ROME?

ROME's concept is totally new. Nobody has ever done what we are developing right now. As well the international project team fits very well, we work together very closely - industry and academia hand in hand.

Date of interview : August 2017
Publication : August 2017

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What are you expecting from the project? Could you give us a concrete example of a benefit that could be expected from ROMEIO?

If we succeed we have a totally new concept of membrane reactors. This concept is supposed to save a huge amount of energy and to reduce emissions.

If ROMEIO is economically efficient at the end, we would be happy to inaugurate the first industrial application for a membrane reactor.

“ ROMEIOs concept is totally new. Nobody has ever done what we are developing right now. ”

What are, according to you, the major challenges to be overcome in ROMEIO?

The major problem will be to have a perfectly operating membrane, there are not only mechanical issues when it comes to operating membrane reactor, but in order to meet our economic goals the membrane has to function very specifically for our case study.

Thanks for your time, Jennifer !

Evonik coordinates the ROMEIO project and participates with two of its' companies: Evonik Performance Materials GmbH and Evonik Technology & Infrastructure GmbH.

Evonik also brings to the project its expertise in hydroformylation catalysis, process intensification, industrial process technology, reactor design and modular plant design. Evonik will be in charge of the demo case for hydroformylation in a near industrial environment.

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